

Text Mining For Identifying Topics About Inclusive Education and ICT

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 05,2025</p> <p>Accepted: July 06 ,2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Inclusive Education, ICT, Text Mining, Topic Model</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15838257</p>	<p><i>Information and communication technologies (ICT) have become a key factor in inclusive education by supporting the access and participation of all people in the educational system. Currently, a large number of works have been published on these topics and it takes time to analyze all the information; for this reason, the objective of this work was to discover and identify hidden and/or relevant topics of 717 abstracts corresponding to research related to inclusive education and ICT published between 1996 and 2020 through text mining. The modelling of themes found 21 topics, the most representative were those related to electronic devices, instructional design, universal learning design and some type of disability or educational need. Three aspects are key to making inclusive education successful: the development of policies, the diversification of educational practices using the principles of universal learning design and the meaningful use of ICT in educational processes. The theme modelling proved to be a useful tool for researchers to analyze large amounts of information and extract the most relevant.</i></p>

Introduction

The use of ICT is recognized by multiple users as an essential part of society because it has generated impacts in various contexts; for example, they have a positive effect on the economic growth of countries (Makun and Jayaraman 2020), it improves productivity in companies (Taştan and Gönel 2020), allows telemedicine (Cissoto, Casarin, and Tomasin 2020), transforms teaching and learning processes (Sosa, Salinas, and Benito 2018). It is currently difficult to determine in which scenarios ICT is not being used; that is why investments and efforts must be made to maximise its benefits and all stakeholders use them in a meaningful way.

One of these scenarios is the educational one, which is constantly changing and must adapt to the dynamics of today's society. One example of this is what has happened worldwide with the COVID-19; where the teaching and learning processes have been transferred to home and students, parents and teachers have made their best effort to continue with the educational process by using ICT in the best way. Undoubtedly, there have been different problems such as the lack of infrastructure (computer equipment, connectivity) and the low level of digital skills that have caused the process to be complex and traumatic for some people; however, it must be understood that ICT becomes an opportunity to “guarantee inclusive, equitable and quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all” (UNESCO 2017, 18). Nevertheless, this is achieved by using them in an innovative way and by recognizing the dynamics of the context where “diversity and different learning needs and abilities, characteristics and expectations of students and communities, eliminating all forms of discrimination” (UNESCO 2008, 3), especially with people who are in vulnerable situations.

In other words, ICT contribute to inclusive education, but because this term has been so controversial (Masih and Vidyapati 2018) it is necessary to define it and understand its scope, for the Colombian Ministry of National Education (MEN, for its acronym in Spanish) it is understood as the

permanent process that recognizes, values and responds in a pertinent way to the diversity of characteristics, interests, possibilities and expectations of girls, boys, adolescents, youth and adults, whose objective is to promote their development, learning and participation, with their peers age, in a common learning environment, without any discrimination or exclusion, and that guarantees, within the framework of human rights, the supports and reasonable adjustments required in their educational process, through practices, policies and cultures that eliminate existing barriers in the educational environment (MEN 2017, 5).

The International Institute for Educational Planning (IIEP) of UNESCO and UNICEF (2019) affirm that inclusive education implies reaching all people and eliminating all barriers (e.g. social, institutional, physical, attitudinal) that could limit the participation and achievement. In accordance with the above, inclusive education is not limited to a specific problem, but must create inclusion strategies for all types of difficulties and ICT have been allied to achieve the inclusion of people in different settings that, due to their difficulties, were found excluded.

According to Cabero and Fernández (2014) the relationship of ICT with inclusive education can be perceived from two points of view, the first is that they favor quality education and eliminate access barriers and the second is that its design promotes the creation of accessible environments, but to achieve this, open and

inclusive policies must be generated to improve the full integration of ICT in institutions where equity is promoted and respond to the diversity of needs (Lieve, Malin, and Barbara 2010) and "eliminate barriers to participation and learning for disadvantaged groups" (D'Alessio, Donnelly, and Watkins 2010, 116).

The Agency Information and Communication Technology for Inclusion (ICT4I) (2013) based on the United Nations Convention on the Rights of People with Disabilities (2006) proposes four principles that should be considered to generate policies towards education of people with disabilities and special educational needs: first, ICT is a key tool to promote equity in educational opportunities, second, access to ICT as a right, third, the training of educational personnel in the use of ICT is a necessity, fourth, research and ICT development requires a multi-stakeholder approach and fifth, monitoring in the use of ICT for inclusion.

In accordance with the above, it is evident that ICTs are a key factor in inclusive education, this is how, in recent decades, research has been developed to address how ICT are used in practice and what impact they have had on people with disabilities (Drigas and Ioannidou 2013; Xie et al. 2020). Among the most relevant topics are: assistive technology (Ismaili and Ibrahim 2017), introduce new teaching and learning methods (Alvarez and Chamorro 2017), the development of skills through ICT (Mavrou and Loizou-Raouna 2017), teacher training (Heo 2010) and policy development (Asongu and Odhiambo 2020). Regardless of the purpose of each investigation, what is sought is to attend the diversity of people through ICT (Cámara, Díaz, and Ortega 2017).

As can be seen, there is a large amount of research related to inclusive education and ICT and extracting and understanding the information takes a lot of time and work (Wang et al. 2016), for this reason, it is necessary to have a greater availability of tools and algorithms that help to explore large collections of documents in alternative and innovative ways, different from traditional searches (Syed and Spruit 2017) that focus on a specific topic (Wang et al. 2016) and run the risk of not detecting relationships between articles (Srivastava and Sahami 2009). One of the alternative ways is text mining that uses natural language (NLP) to transform unstructured text such as articles, summaries, tweets into structured texts suitable for statistical analysis (Dai et al. 2014) or perform machine-learning algorithms to find patterns and/or trends hidden within texts (Talabis et al. 2015).

In this study, topic modelling specifically the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) was used to perform text mining on abstracts of published work on inclusive education and ICT to discover and identify hidden and relevant textual patterns. This is followed by a short presentation on topic modelling and LDA.

Topic Models

They are algorithms that allow discovering latent thematic structures (i.e. topics) from a large collection of documents (Blei 2012) and offer a probabilistic framework to automatically classify or summarise documents that would be difficult to classify manually (Syed and Spruit 2017) and they do it with greater speed and quantitative rigor (Grimmer and Stewart 2013). In general, topic modelling consists of finding a group of topics from a collection of documents that best represents the information in all documents.

There are different techniques to obtain topic models. The best known are Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA), Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA), Explicit Semantic Analysis (ESA), Correlated Topics Model (CTM) and Hierarchical Dirichlet Process (HDP); for this work LDA was chosen because it is a powerful and popular method according to Hansen (2018).

Latent Dirichlet Allocation

LDA was initially explained by Blei, Ng, and Jordan (2003) and they define it as "a generative probabilistic model for collections of discrete data such as text corpora" (993), which "aims to uncover latent or hidden thematic structures from a corpus. The latent thematic structure, expressed as topics and topic proportions per document, is represented by hidden variables that LDA posits onto the corpus" (Syed and Spruit 2017, 2).

Without delving into the mathematical part, LDA is guided by two principles: the first is that every document is a mixture of topics and the second is that every topic is a mixture of words (Silge and Robinson 2020) and the model estimates those two probabilities applying statistical inference techniques to find the most probable latent structure of the documents (Syed and Spruit 2017). For example, if you have a corpus of 4 documents, LDA discovers the topics and determines which words belong to that topic (e.g. topic 1: 40% breakfast, 15% lunch, 10% dinner ..., it can be interpreted that they are meals, topic 2: 35% beans, 15% lentils ..., can be interpreted as grains). In addition, it determines the probability of each topic present in the documents (e.g. document 1 and 2: 100% of topic 1, document 3: 60% of topic 1 and 40% of topic 2, document 4: 100% of topic 2).

The number of topics is not determined by LDA but is an a priori parameter provided by the user and there is no formal way to calculate it. Usually, the researcher can select it or can use approaches used by other authors, for this work it was used The Harmonic Mean proposed by Ponweiser (2012), which consists of making

LDA iterations with different K values and subsequently with the results of the obtained probabilities, the harmonic mean is calculated, and the optimal K value is determined to apply LDA.

In summary, LDA provides two results, the topics, and their weights in each document, in the R studio computer program that is used in this work, the first result is Word-topic probabilities called β ("beta") and the second Document- topic probabilities called γ ("gamma").

Method

Data Set

The data of this work were obtained from a search carried out in Scopus and Web of Science (WoS), the search strategy focused on two topics: inclusive education and ICT, the search string was: ("inclusive education" OR "educational inclusion") AND (technology * OR ict OR "Information and Communication Technology"). 431 works and 547 of WoS published from 1996 to the first semester of 2020 were found in Scopus. All abstracts were downloaded, and those repeated records were eliminated, leaving a total of 717 abstracts to perform the modelling of themes.

Data Set

The modelling of themes was carried out with the program Rstudio Version 1.2.5042, the process carried out was: first, the 717 abstracts were loaded into the program, second, the data was converted into a corpus (structured data to work on the software), third, a pre-processing was carried out that consisted of eliminating from the data everything that did not contribute information to the work. Also, words such as numbers, special characters, stopwords, punctuation, extra whitespace, general words like background, aim, method, result, conclusion and the search keywords were eliminated to avoid deficient discriminatory information due to its presence in almost all retrieved abstracts (Wang et al. 2016) additionally all words were converted to lowercase.

Fourth, a combination of minimum and maximum frequencies was established to focus on the common but distinctive characteristics within the text (Watanabe and Stefan 2020), fifth, a document matrix was constructed, which is a table that contains the frequency of words (Silge and Robinson 2020). Sixth, the optimal number of subjects (k) was determined by applying the Harmonic Mean proposed by Ponweiser (2012); to do this, a sequence of models of subjects with different values of K was created. Then, LDA was applied for each value of K, later, the harmonic mean of all the obtained models was calculated. For this work, the harmonic mean gave that the optimal number of topics was $K = 21$.

Seventh, the LDA topic modelling was executed, where a "topic can be described as a multinomial distribution of words, and a single document can be described as a multinomial distribution of latent topics" (Wang et al. 2016, 2). The model obtains per-topic word distributions $P(\text{word}|\text{topic})$ called β ("beta") and per document topic distributions $P(\text{topic}|\text{document})$ called γ ("gamma"), β determines the probability of the words associated with each topic and γ determines the probability of the documents associated with each topic.

Data Analysis

For the data analysis, the two results of LDA β and γ were taken into account. The first thing that was done was to visualize the words associated with each topic using word clouds, where the largest words are those that have a greater probability of belonging to the topic. The second thing was to relate the words and give a name to the topics and in those topics where the relationship was not evident, the most probable works associated with each topic were analyzed and finally, through the gamma probability, the most popular topics were determined.

Results

The objective of this work was to discover relevant topics of the different summaries related to Inclusive Education and ICT through text mining, for this LDA was used, which allows the unsupervised classification of documents based on probabilistic vectors of words. The model was applied to 717 abstracts between 1996 and the first half of 2020. It should be noted that 53% of the published documents belong to the last 4 years. In addition, the Harmonic Mean was used to calculate the number of topics, for this work it was $K = 21$. As mentioned above, LDA produces two results: the first is the beta probability (β) of the words associated with each topic and the second is the gamma probability (γ) of the documents associated with each topic. Figure 1 shows the word cloud associated with each topic based on the probability β .

develops its study based on the inclusion of gender, Mejía (2019) on functional diversity in the university, Vasconcelos et al. (2017) on the admission of older citizens to university. Additionally, these studies affirm that inequity can be reduced through inclusive education and ICT. Topic 11 is the research that takes place in rural areas. For example, Stenman and Pettersson (2020) propose the remote teaching strategy, Morales (2017) analyses the relationship between the digital context and rural areas both in students and in old people.

Topic 12 are works related to dyslexia, Stampoltzis and Polychronopoulou (2008). They discuss results in the light of inclusive education and equal opportunities; Diraä et al. (2009) evaluate two assistive technologies for people with this difficulty. Topic 13 are studies that investigate hearing impairment, Munoz et al. (2013) determine strategic factors that can facilitate an inclusive education for the deaf, Timoteo et al. (2018) use adaptive technologies for this population and Kourbetis, Boukouras, and Gelastopoulou (2016) analyse innovative interactive applications for the education of deaf students. Topic 14 are works related to autism spectrum disorders (ASD). For example, Aysina et al. (2019) work on the factors that determine the preparation of educators to teach children with ASD and Ntalindwa et al. (2019) investigated the perceptions of both children, parents and teachers about the use of ICT.

Topic 15 refers to Universal Design for Learning (UDL). The research by Sholanke et al. (2018) evaluates teaching methods based on the principles of UDL, Riviou, Kouroupetroglou, and Oikonomidis (2015) present the UDLnet network, which aims to contribute to improving the practice of teachers by combining ICT skills and the UDL, Alvarez and Chamorro (2017) propose didactic strategies for the incorporation of the UDL. Topic 16 are works that use different electronic devices to support inclusive education. For example, the use of computers and mobile devices (Hong 2018). When observing the word cloud of topic 17, no relationship is evident between the words, but when reading the most representative documents, it was found that most of the investigations were carried out in Russia and their objectives were diverse, such as: the study of curative pedagogy (Shmachilina-Tsybenko and Bud'ko2017), problems and perspectives of inclusive sport (Mikhaylova et al. 2018), inclusive culture as a component of professional and pedagogical culture (Ketrish et al. 2019) and Humanitarian Technologies of Inclusive Education (Nigmatov 2014).

As for topic 8, topic 18 also responds to two topics. The first refers to Science, Technology, Engineering and Math (STEM). For example, Arredondo, Vázquez, and Velázquez (2019) determine the need for STEM teaching to reduce gender inequality, Asghar et al. (2017) use STEM to support the cognitive development of students with learning disabilities (LD), Tsiastoudis and Polatoglou (2018) develop a course on STEM for people with disabilities in the classroom and the second topic refers to the use of augmented reality (AR) to improve various skills of students with difficulties (Khowaja et al. 2020). In topic 19, the same thing happens as in topic 17: it does not find any relationship of the words. However, when reading it, it was found that the investigations show the need for teacher training in inclusive education and ICT (Alegre and Villar 2019).

Topic 20 focuses in a general way on special educational needs (SEN). For example, Rito (2018) designed an activity through ICT to be used by children with difficulties, Jacob et al. (2010) adapted an assistive technology to the context and Han (2019) uses group creative thinking technologies to solve problems in an inclusive educational environment. Finally, topic 21 is work related to e-learning. For example, Melliou, Bratitsis, and Salmon (2018) determine the potential of a virtual community to overcome inequalities and Laabidi et al. (2014) analyze the accessible version of Moodle platform. Table 1 shows the topics with the given names and the five most probable words obtained when applying the LDA model.

Table 1. The most five probable words in the topics of LDA

T1: Competences development	competence-foreign-formative-key-aspects
T2: Developmental disabilities	developmental-vision-become-appropriate-impairment
T3: Instructional design/instruction	instructional-instruction-class-english-mainstream
T4:Speech disorders	speech-competences-communities-cognitive-book
T5: Visual assistive technologies	braille-reading-mathematical-software-resource
T6: Changes	change-music-occupational-approaches-musical
T7: Intellectual disability	intellectual-media-syndrome-right-individual
T8: Preservice – Game	preservice-games-game-abilities-classrooms
T9: Policies	policy-ministry-policies-government-rights
T10: Inequity/Inequality	functional-population-senior-economy-female
T11: Rural areas	rural-areas-collaborative-universal-material
T12: Dyslexia	groups-dyslexia-tolerance-community-requirements
T13: Hearing impairment	deaf-sign-preschool-text-brazilian
T14: Autism spectrum disorders (ASD)	asd-web-blind-contemporary-emotions

T15: Universal Desing for Learning	udl-universal-principles-policies-regular
T16: Electronic devices	devices-mobile-interface-computer-software
T17: Russia	modern-problem-formation-activity-theoretical
T18: STEM – Augmented reality	engineering-stem-ar-augmented-reality
T19: Teacher training	impairment-adolescents-play-elementary-early
T20: Special Needs Education	autism-sen-distance-spectrum-disorder
T21: E-learning	online-eLearning-distance-countries-institution

udl: Universal Desing for Learning, *sen*: Special Educational Needs, *stem*: Science, Technology, Engineering and Math, *ar*:Augmented Reality, *asd*: Autism spectrum disorder

According to the gamma probability (γ) the most popular topics in relation to Inclusive Education and ICT are: T16: Electronic devices, T1: Competences development, T3: Instructional design/instruction, T15: Universal Design for Learning, T20: Special Needs Education. Figure 2 shows the number of documents with the highest probabilities (greater than 90%) associated with each topic.

Figure 2. Documents with a probability greater than 90% of being associated with each topic.

Discussion

Text mining in recent years has become an important tool to recover, interpret and understand the current state of a topic and propose future lines of research (Wang, et al. 2016). In this research, LDA topic modelling was applied and 21 topics related to inclusive education and ICT were obtained. Some of the topics found can be grouped together. The first group has to do with work related to some type of disability or some special educational need, these are T2: Developmental disabilities, T4: Speech disorders, T7: Intellectual disability, T12: Dyslexia, T13: Hearing impairment, T14: Autism Spectrum Disorders (ASD) and T20: Special Needs Education. Group 2 focuses on studying other barriers that can affect inclusive education such as, inequity/inequality (T11) and work in rural areas (T12). Following the same line as Cabero and Fernández (2014), what these two groups seek is to eliminate those barriers that exclude people from participating and having equity in educational opportunities.

In relation to the two previous groups, it is observed that most of the works focus on people who have some SEN but more research is needed in the second group; for example, how ICT has contributed to the educational inclusion of the people who have some condition of vulnerability (e.g. immigrants, victims of violence, situation of poverty, race or sex discrimination).

Group 3 are topics directly related to ICT (T16) and assistive technologies (T15) that “can provide the means for many learners to engage in educational activities equitably alongside their peers” (ICT4I 2013, 13). In this group there are also the technologies that several authors have called emerging (new), such as augmented reality (T18) (Marín-Díaz 2017). One of the challenges for researchers is to be able to create, use and/or adapt emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, the internet of things, Machine Learning Education Applications, among others, to support inclusive education.

Group 4 are topics that promote the creation of accessible learning environments (Cabero and Fernández 2014) and innovative through tools such as games or gamification (T8), e-learning (T20), the use of

STEM (T18) and the instructional design or instruction (T3), but to achieve these, it is necessary to generate teacher training plans (T19) both initial and continuous that allow teachers to acquire the skills to face new challenges and be able to link the pedagogical facts with the educational and social reality (Carrion 2020), in order to achieve an inclusive education, driven by quality and capable of responding to the characteristics of the students (Pegalajar 2018). The remaining topics are not grouped because each of them responds to a particular theme, such as policies (T9) and the universal design of learning (T15) that were mentioned in the previous section.

LDA also determines the most popular topics that allow to give a general look of what is being investigated and observe the topics where there are gaps to be studied. In this work, some of the main gaps found were studies on policies and teacher training in inclusive education and ICT, which were also found in works by Toquero (2020) and Alegre and Villar (2019). The foregoing does not imply that they stop working on the other topics, on the contrary, they must be strengthened and generated a synergy among all to achieve an inclusive education where people in a vulnerable condition have equal opportunities and can access, participate and feel included and not excluded from the educational system and as mentioned by IC4T (2013) and Drigas and Ioannidou (2013), ICT become a key factor or the bridge to guarantee the social inclusion of people.

As can be seen, the modelling of LDA topics allows to capture implicit patterns within the text through mathematical algorithms, but it still has some limitations. For example, this research found topics that could have been included in a single topic as was in the case of topic 14 and 20. It also found topics that did not respond only to one category, such as T8 and T18 and some topics such as T17 and T19. When observing the most probable words of each one, no relationship was found and to find it, it was necessary to perform the reading of the most representative documents. This could happen because a good pre-processing of the data was not carried out and/or the number of topics found was not optimal because the methods that are proposed for their calculation are iterative and each time data are run in the software they may vary and may not always give the same result. For this reason, in modelling, the judgment of the researcher is essential to determine the number of topics that is optimal. That is, a model that does not repeat or leaves out some topics (Wang et al. 2016) and this is achieved by making several iterations of the model. Another limitation of LDA is not being able to find the relationships between the topics automatically. In this research, the grouping was carried out based on the researcher's expertise; for future works other tools should be used to find the similarity between topics.

Finally, this study worked with abstracts that have a limited number of words and may not adequately convey the heterogeneity of the research topics that are part of the document (Syed and Spruit, 2017). For this reason, it is recommended that the following research use the complete documents to perform an optimal pre-processing of the information and thus, discover latent themes and recapture known facts (Wang, et al. 2016).

Conclusion

This study applied LDA topic modelling to abstracts related to inclusive education and ICT. The results showed the ability of the model to separate different documents into different topics and proved to be a useful tool for researchers to analyse large amounts of information and extract the most important.

Finally, to make inclusive education successful it is necessary to generate a synergy between all the users involved to establish policies (e.g. in infrastructure, in initial and continuing teacher training); diversify educational practices within the framework of the principles of universal design for learning and significantly use ICT in educational processes. These three elements are key factors that allow ALL people to have access, participation and equal opportunities in the educational system and thus guaranteeing a quality education that promotes the development and strengthening of the necessary competencies to face the challenges of society.

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